

Evidence for in-plane spin-flop orientation at MnPt/Fe(100) interface revealed by x-ray magnetic linear dichroism

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(Dated: 26th January 2006)

X-ray magnetic linear and circular dichroism at the Mn $L_{2,3}$ edges are used to determine the magnetic properties of epitaxial MnPt films on Fe(100). The good agreement between experimental linear dichroism and multiplet calculations reveals that the Mn spins are aligned in plane but perpendicularly to the underlying in-plane Fe spins. The absence of magnetic circular dichroism rules out the presence of uncompensated Mn spins at the interface.

PACS numbers: 75.25.+z, 75.70.-i, 75.70.R

Keywords: soft x-ray absorption, magnetic linear dichroism, exchange bias coupling

The exchange bias effect is currently of great interest because of its application for magnetic devices with spin valves and magnetic tunnel junctions [1, 2], where the local magnetic structure at the antiferromagnet/ferromagnet (AFM/FM) interface plays a key role [3–9]. The observation of pinned spins at the AFM/FM interface was recently reported for polycrystalline sandwiches used in room temperature device structures [10], including metallic or insulating AFM materials. It has been speculated that the origin of the uncompensated pinned spins resides at the grain boundaries and that the size of their contribution can quantitatively explain the macroscopic exchange bias using a simple modified model [11, 12]. Moreover, the relationship between crystallographic direction and magnetization reversal, due to the influence of the unidirectional anisotropy has been recently addressed in MnPd films [13]. In spite of extensive experimental and theoretical research the basic mechanism of this effect is still unclear, and a better control of the factors affecting the AFM/FM interface formation is highly desired. Since an appropriate choice of the substrate (or seeding layer) to reduce the lattice mismatch and the surface morphology are playing an important role in the magnitude of the exchange bias, epitaxy-based techniques may enable a better understanding of the influence of interfacial effects on magnetic properties.

MnPt is a AuCu-I type ordered alloy with a room temperature magnetic moment of $4.3 \mu_B$ [14]. The Néel temperature is 970 K, which makes MnPt – and similar alloys like MnPd and MnIr – appealing materials acting as a pinning layer for giant magnetoresistance (GMR) devices. Moreover, MnPt has a tetragonal structure with lattice parameters $a = 4.00 \text{ \AA}$ and $c/a = 0.92$, hence Fe(100) is a very good candidate for epitaxial growth because its lattice parameter ($2.87 \text{ \AA}$) favors a small mismatch of 1.5% with the overlayer oriented with the c -axis perpendicular to the sample surface. Exchange bias effects have been observed for polycrystalline MnPt thin

film when the bilayer was made with FeNi or FeCo [15]. Recent experiments on PtMn/NiFe exchange-biased bilayers grown by molecular beam epitaxy (MBE) have shown that the magnetic moments might be antiferromagnetically aligned parallel or normal to the interface [16–18]. In particular, the delicate interplay of interfacial magnetism with chemical and structural order has been recently demonstrated in the epitaxial growth of Fe on thick PtMn films [19].

Here we investigated with use of x-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) and x-ray magnetic linear and circular dichroism (XMLD and XMCD) at the Mn and Fe $L_{2,3}$ edges the magnetic structure of thin MnPt films with well defined phase and thickness, epitaxially grown on the Fe(100) interface. We find a clear XMLD signal at the Mn edges for in-plane sample magnetization indicating that the Mn magnetic moments are aligned parallel to the surface. The XAS and XMLD measurements are compared with multiplet calculations to obtain information about the ground state properties of this system. It turns out that the XMLD is related to AFM domains aligned perpendicularly to the Fe magnetization axis. The absence of an XMCD signal excludes the presence of uncompensated Mn spins at the interface.

The measurements were performed at room temperature on the APE undulator beamline at the Elettra synchrotron radiation facility. The Fe(3%Si)(100) single crystal was prepared through repeated cycles of Ar⁺ sputtering and annealing at 400°C. The presence of Si, C and P segregated impurities, as revealed by Auger electron spectroscopy, was further confirmed by the sharp $c(2 \times 2)$ low-energy electron diffraction (LEED) patterns [20]. An 8 ML thick MnPt film was grown on Fe(100) by *in situ* co-evaporation. The base pressure in the sample preparation chamber was 4×10^{-11} mbar and during deposition the pressure remained below 2×10^{-10} mbar. After the deposition the Fe Auger peaks retain a sizeable intensity and we observe a (1×1) LEED pattern,

Figure 1: (Color online) X-ray absorption spectra of 8 ML MnPt/Fe(100) and 8 ML Mn/Fe(100). The spectra are normalized to the L_3 peak maximum and shifted vertically for clarity. Both spectra were taken with x-rays at normal incidence to the surface. The conventional cell of epitaxial MnPt is rotated by 45° with respect to the $\{100\}$ surface directions of the underlying Fe substrate, as shown in the inset.

thus confirming that the MnPt grows with the c -axis perpendicular to the surface, so that Mn and Pt grow as alternating layers, i.e., Mn (Pt) followed by Pt (Mn), etc. After the deposition, Si and C disappeared from the Auger spectra and only a small residual (<0.1 ML) P remains, indicating that Si and C are not present in the MnPt film. In order to prevent oxidation the film was capped with 4 ML Pt. Magnetic dichroism measurements were done with the sample magnetized in plane at remanence, after transfer in UHV to the analysis chamber. The absorption spectra were recorded by collecting the total electron yield (TEY) using the sample drain current. A spot size in the order of $120 \mu\text{m}$ was used. The typical size of the ferromagnetic single domains of the Fe(100) substrate was $0.5 \mu\text{m}$, as measured in the same experimental chamber using spin polarization in Mott scattering experiments. The x-ray beam was at normal incidence with fixed polarization and the sample was rotated about the surface normal, to obtain E_π (E_σ) parallel (perpendicular) to M , where E is the linear polarization direction of the light and M is the substrate magnetization direction, which is along the Fe[100]. In order to cross-check the possible presence of an instrumental asymmetry, we also recorded the spectra with the sample rotated about the normal by 180° . The final results are averaged over the two data sets.

Figure 1 shows the Mn $L_{2,3}$ XAS of the MnPt film capped with 4 ML Pt. The most remarkable features are the distinctly split structure of the L_2 edge and the two weak shoulders in the high-energy tail of the L_3 . A similar behavior has been observed for $3d$ metals with reduced coordination number, such as for sub-monolayer deposition of Mn on Cu, Fe and Ni [21–23] where the $3d$ orbitals are more localized than in the bulk. Our sample is a thin layer containing only four bilayers of alternating Mn and Pt layers, which suggests that, although the system is an intermetallic alloy, the Mn $3d$ states have some degree of electron correlation. The XAS is compared with that of 8 ML Mn film grown on Fe in order to verify the absence of any contamination during deposition, because the double peak structure of the L_2 peak and the shoulders for the L_3 are also features of Mn oxide. From the quality of the spectrum for the pure metallic Mn deposited under identical experimental conditions as the MnPt film we are confident that the double peak structure of the L_2 in MnPt is not caused by contamination.

Figure 2: (Color online) XAS (top) and XMLD (bottom) spectra for 8 ML MnPt/Fe(100). Comparison between experimental (thick black line) and calculated (thin red line) spectra. The inset depicts the experimental geometry, showing the axes of the Fe(100) substrate. The sample was in-plane magnetized at remanence. The orientation of the linear polarization with respect to the magnetization is indicated by π (parallel) and σ (perpendicular).

We measured the Mn $L_{2,3}$ XMLD both for normal incidence and at grazing angle. The dichroism is in the order of 1%. Figure 2 shows the isotropic spectrum and the linear dichroism (signal $\times 20$) for normal incidence. The XMLD is the difference $E_\sigma - E_\pi$. The presence of an XMLD signal demonstrates that the magnetic moments of the Mn atoms are aligned antiferromagnetically. As we will also show further on, the Mn atoms show no net magnetic moment.

For comparison with the experimental results Fig. 2 also shows the calculated spectra normalized to the Mn L_3 peak maximum. The spectra are calculated with atomic multiplet theory in intermediate coupling using Cowan's *ab initio* Hartree-Fock code with relativistic correction [24] and in the presence of crystal field. Details of the calculations can be found in [25, 26]. A small octahedral crystal field of $10Dq = 0.15$ eV is needed to obtain a line shape of the XMLD compatible with experimental data. A larger crystal field gives a less good agreement, which proves that we are not dealing with an oxide, which would have a crystal field larger than 1 eV.

Comparison of the experimental spectra with calculations is essential to determine the spin axis [27]. In fact, the calculated XMLD spectrum agrees with the experimental curve only for the case that the AFM domains are aligned *perpendicularly* to the Fe magnetization axis, thus providing evidence for *in-plane* spin-flop of the Mn magnetic moments, in contrast with the typical AFM orientation of bulk MnPt along the c axis (the [001] direction of the conventional cell, which in our case is perpendicular to the surface). This result also differs from a recent XMLD study on a single Mn layer deposited on Fe(100), where the entire non-collinear magnetic structure of Mn is perpendicular to the interface [28].

The magnitude of the theoretical dichroism is about six times larger than the experimental result, which could have several reasons. First of all, the theoretical XMLD is obtained for Mn d^5 atoms with a magnetic moment of $5 \mu_B$, which exceeds the value of $4.3 \mu_B$ expected for MnPt at room temperature. The magnitude of the XMLD depends mainly on $\langle M^2 \rangle$, since for d^5 in the cubic symmetry the contribution of the charge quadrupole moment is negligible, however a reduction in $\langle M^2 \rangle$ by a factor of six seems hard to explain if all moments are perfectly aligned antiferromagnetically. The XMLD was

Figure 3: (Color online) Experimental Mn $L_{2,3}$ XMLD (thick black line) for 8 ML MnPt/Fe(100) measured at normal (0°) and grazing (55° off-normal) incidence. The spectra are shifted vertically and are compared to theoretical calculations (thin red line) with $10Dq = 0.15$ eV. The inset shows the experimental geometry, where the XMLD is given as the difference $E_\sigma - E_\pi$.

measured at remanence, and part of the spins might be aligned along the surface magnetization axis and/or perpendicular to the surface. This fact might have implications for the understanding of exchange bias (AFM/FM) systems, where it is common to find that the exchange interaction is an order of magnitude smaller than expected.

To further investigate this point we also measured the XMLD with the x-ray beam at 55° off-normal incidence, making only a small angle with the substrate magnetization M (see inset of Fig. 3). This grazing incidence geometry makes the XMLD sensitive to the anisotropy in the plane normal to M , and hence measures the AFM spin orientation in that plane. Figure 3 shows that both the overall shape and the magnitude of the XMLD measured at 55° off-normal are quite similar to those for normal incidence. The maximum of the L_3 XMLD is larger while the other features are similar in size. In the L_2 region the first feature is slightly enhanced, and the second one is more pronounced. If the Mn spins would have been aligned along M then the magnitude of the XMLD for 55° would be three times smaller than that for 0° [29]. The results clearly show that the AFM domains are mainly in the surface plane and perpendicular to M , and that out-of-plane spin orientation would be quite small.

Another possible reason for the reduced XMLD would be the presence of uncompensated spins at the AFM/FM interface belonging to the AFM material which results in a net ferromagnetic orientation. This can be probed with XMCD, and the results are shown in Fig. 4. The Mn $L_{2,3}$ spectra were collected with the incident x-rays at 45° with the direction of the applied magnetic field. The absence of any visible XMCD signal for Mn confirms the AFM nature of the MnPt film and the absence of any FM substrate influence which could induce FM ordering of the Mn atoms, e.g., due to deep intermixing and/or alloying at the interface [30, 31]. The persistence of the (1×1) LEED pattern after the deposition is consistent with these considerations. On the other hand, the overlayer thickness was chosen to have still a detectable Fe TEY signal. The XMCD measured at the Fe $L_{2,3}$ edges (not shown here) agrees with the magnitude reported in the literature for the bulk, from which we can infer a single-domain magnetic structure for the underlying substrate. We note that the Fe XMCD originates from the interface region because the sampling depth of the TEY signal (determined by the electron inelastic mean free

Figure 4: (Color online) XAS and XMCD measured at 45° incidence angle with the magnetization direction. The XMCD has been multiplied by 20. The XAS lineshape is averaged over the two spectra measured with opposite circular polarizations. The Mn XAS is identical to that of Fig. 1

path) is ~ 50 Å [32] and the interface is ~ 15 Å below the surface.

In conclusion, the combined experimental and theoretical analysis of the epitaxial interface MnPt/Fe(001) enabled us to identify an in-plane orientation of the Mn magnetic moments driven by a spin-flop mechanism leading to a dominant orientation of the AFM domains perpendicular to the substrate magnetization. We cannot exclude competition with in-plane AFM domains oriented parallel to the applied magnetization to explain the reduced magnitude of the XMLD. The absence of uncompensated spins is confirmed by the XMCD measurements. It is tempting to associate the absence of pinning configurations with the presence of a ‘smooth’ interface, as produced by ideal epitaxial growth.

We would like to thank M. Fabrizio and A. Stollo for technical support of the experiment. This work was supported by INFN-CNR.

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Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4